

**Structural, Dielectric, Vibrational and Semiconducting Properties of
Ferroelectric-Photovoltaic $\text{Bi}(\text{Ni}_{1/3}\text{Nb}_{2/3})\text{O}_3\text{-PbTiO}_3$ material**

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In this study, We demonstrate the development of $(1-x)\text{Bi}(\text{Ni}_{2/3}\text{Nb}_{1/3})\text{O}_3-x\text{PbTiO}_3$ (BNN-PT) samples with composition ($x=0, 0.77, 0.70, 0.65, 0.625, 0.60, 0.55$) using the conventional solid-state reaction technique .

Phase identification and structural characterization of sintered BNN-PT powders for all compositions were made by X-Ray diffraction technique. The Optical, structural, magnetic, ferroelectric and dielectric properties were measured for all compositions. The Raman mode A1 shifts to lower frequency and the average grain size decreases with BNN doping which is due to difference in ionic radii of Ti and Ni. The ferromagnetic properties of BNN-PT improved with increasing the doping concentration of Ni. The optical band gap reduced from 3.0 eV to 2.1 eV with varying the BNN doping in BNN-PT. It is observed that band gap of BNN-PT depends on doping percentage of Ni. The reduced band gap makes the BNN-PT promising material for ferroelectric photovoltaic applications.

Keywords: X-ray diffraction, Perovskite, Photovoltaic, Ferro-electric.